

Kakhiani M.

Prof.

Beridze T.

Assoc. Prof.

Nozadze N.

Assoc. Prof.

Abstract

In the work is considers the conditions of vehicle high passability and satisfying turn ability with the purpose of that improvement are offered structures of pulsating differential, consisting of full-length spherical or elliptical spurs and being in gearing with them the toroidal gears, which partial length teeth are located along in the spatial curves. The presented differential provides the for change in a large range of traction force, blocking the slipping, providing the high possibility and satisfying requirements.

Keywords: pulsating differential, possibility, blocking ratio, maneuverability, slipping, gear ratio, adjustment range.

In order to ensure high cross-country capacity and satisfactory turn ability of vehicles, it is rational for the differential located between the driving semi-axes to have a blocking coefficient $K_g = 2,5...4$. For average road conditions at $K_g=4$, the probability of fully using the cohesion is 93.8%, at $K_g=3$ - respectively 85% [1].

In "Chevrolet" cars by firm "Tickman" instead of a differential located between the driving axle shafts, a pulsating differential is used [2]. On Fig. 1.a,b,c is presented a scheme of a differential with round bevel gears with a variable gear ratio. This differential is distinguished by the fact that special profile teeth are used

(Fig. 1.d), due that gear ratio in the pair of satellite-axle shaft gear changes jointly with the change in the relative position of their teeth. The number of satellite teeth is odd, therefore, when it rotates, the engagement is in different phases with the teeth of the right and left axle shafts. The profiles of the teeth of the satellites and axle shaft are selected in such a way that the maximum gear ratio in the satellite-axle shaft gear pair is obtained in the case when the base of the tooth of the satellite is engaged with the head of the tooth of the driven gear of axle shaft, and the minimum gear ratio is obtained when the head of the tooth of the satellite is engaged with the base of the tooth of the axle shaft gear.

Fig. 1. Scheme of pulsating differential operation

Therefore, for the position shown in Fig. 1.a), the maximum torque on the differential box is transferred to the left axle shaft, and for the position shown in Fig. 1.c) - to the right axle shaft. For the position of Fig. 1.b) the load on the differential box was distributed equally between the axle shafts. For the differential under consideration $K_g < 1,25$ [3,4].

Let's consider the interaxle pulsating differential with variable gear ratio [3,4]. The differential consists of elliptical bevel gears 1, 2 (Fig. 2), rigidly fixed on the half-axes 3, 4 of the driving wheels A and B. Gears 1, 2 are in engagement with satellites 5 that freely rotate

on the axes 6, located in the differential housing 7. A round bevel gear 8 is connected to the differential housing 7, freely rotating on the shafts of the half-axes 3, 4 that are in engagement with the bevel gear 9, rigidly attached to the cardan shaft 10. Transmission 1, 5, 2 would be consisting of non-circular bevel gears with undeformed (Fig. 4) or deformed axoids. For a differential with variable gear ratio $K_g = (U_{12}^7)_{\max}$, where the gear ratio U_{12}^7 of gears 1, 5, 2 in the case of stationary housing 7. For elliptical-bevel gears 1, 5, 2 with an average gear ratio in a simple row $n = 1$ we obtain

$$(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = \left(\frac{1+e}{1-e}\right)^2, (u_{12}^7)_{\min} = \left(\frac{1-e}{1+e}\right)^2, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Bevel differential with undeformed elliptical gears

where $e=1,5,2$ is the value of 1, 5, 2 gears eccentricity. When $e=0,33$, $(U_{12}^7)_{\max} = 3,94$, $(U_{12}^7)_{\min} = 0,254$, when $e=0,225$, $(U_{12}^7)_{\max} = 2,5$, $K_g = 2,5$. Let's accept $K_g = -3,94$. As $(U_{12}^7)_{\max} \neq (U_{12}^7)_{\min}$ differential is non-symmetric.

In the case of a vehicle moving along a straight section of the road, wheels A and B have the same coefficients of adhesion to the road, the relationship between the angular velocities of the differential rings will be as following

$$\omega_2 = \frac{(1 + u_{12}^7) \omega_7 - \omega_1}{u_{12}^7}, \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_7$ – are the angular velocities of gears 1, 2 and differential 7.

In the case when a vehicle moves along a straight section of the road and equal resistance forces act on wheels A and B, housing 7, gears 1, 5, 2 rotate jointly and provide the same distribution of angular velocities and torques on wheels A and B. In the case when the vehicle moves along a curvilinear section of the road, where wheels A and B have different coefficients of cohesion to the road, wheels 1 and 2 receive additional rotational motion, satellite 5 rotates around axis 6, and the whole mechanism operates as a differential. However, the angular velocities on the outer and inner wheels vary within the following range:

$$\begin{aligned} [(\omega_B)_{\text{gamswr.}}]_{\min} &= 1,254\omega_7 - 0,254\omega_A; [(\omega_B)_{\text{gamswr.}}]_{\max} = 4,93\omega_7 - 3,93\omega_A; \\ [(\omega_A)_{\text{Camomr.}}]_{\max} &= 4,93\omega_7 - 3,93\omega_B; [(\omega_A)_{\text{Camomr.}}]_{\min} = 1,254\omega_7 - 0,254\omega_B. \end{aligned}$$

The torques on the outer and inner wheels vary within the following range:

$$\begin{aligned} [(T_B)_{\text{gamswr.}}]_{\min} &= \frac{T_7}{1 - (u_{12}^7)_{\max}} = 0,202T_7; [(T_A)_{\text{gamswr.}}]_{\max} \approx \frac{T_7 (u_{12}^7)_{\max}}{(u_{12}^7)_{\max} - 1} = 0,797T_7; \\ [(T_B)_{\text{Camomr.}}]_{\max} &= \frac{T_7}{1 - (u_{12}^7)_{\min}} = 0,797T_7; [(T_A)_{\text{Camomr.}}]_{\min} \approx \frac{T_7 (u_{12}^7)_{\min}}{(u_{12}^7)_{\min} - 1} = 0,202T_7; \end{aligned}$$

where T_7 is the torque acting on the differential housing.

When one gear is stopped, the angular velocities and torques are calculated using the relations:

$$\text{when } \omega_A = 0: (\omega_B)_{\max} = 4,94\omega_7; (\omega_B)_{\min} = 1,254\omega_7; (T_B)_{\max} = 0,797T_7; (T_B)_{\min} = 0,202T_7,$$

$$\text{when } \omega_B = 0: (\omega_A)_{\max} = 4,94\omega_7; (\omega_A)_{\min} = 1,254\omega_7; (T_A)_{\max} = 0,797T_7; (T_A)_{\min} = 0,202T_7.$$

When wheel A slips, gear 1 receives additional rotational motion, and wheel B performs movement with variable angular velocity. The angular velocities of wheel B and the torques of wheels A and B vary within the range:

$$\begin{aligned} (\omega_B)_{\min} &= 1,254\omega_7 - 0,254\omega_A; & (\omega_B)_{\max} &= 4,93\omega_7 - 3,93\omega_A; & (T_A)_{\max} &= 0,797T_7; \\ (T_A)_{\min} &= 0,202T_7; & (T_B)_{\min} &= 0,202T_7; & (T_B)_{\max} &= 0,797T_7. \end{aligned}$$

If slips the wheel B : $(\omega_A)_{\max} = 4,94\omega_7 - 3,94\omega_B$; $(\omega_A)_{\min} = 1,254\omega_7 - 0,254\omega_B$;
 $(T_A)_{\max} = 0,797T_7$; $(T_A)_{\min} = 0,202T_7$; $(T_B)_{\min} = 0,202T_7$; $(T_B)_{\max} = 0,979T_7$.

At simultaneously sliding of wheels A and B : $(\omega_B)_{\max} = 4,94\omega_7 - 3,94\omega_A$;
 $(\omega_B)_{\min} = 1,254\omega_7 - 0,254\omega_A$; $(T_B)_{\min} = 0,202T_7$; $(T_B)_{\max} = 0,797T_7$;
 $(\omega_A)_{\max} = 4,94\omega_7 - 3,94\omega_B$; $(\omega_A)_{\min} = 1,254\omega_7 - 0,254\omega_B$; $(T_A)_{\max} = 0,797T_7$;
 $(T_A)_{\min} = 0,202T_7$.

The frequency of parameters ω_A ; ω_B ; T_A ; T_B ; change depends on the coefficient of deformation of the axoids of 1, 5, 2 gears; for gears with undeformed axoids – is equal to 180° , for gears with a coefficient of deformation of the axoids equal to three – 120° .

The following conclusions would be drawn from the obtained dependencies:

1. During the period corresponding to satellite turning by 180° ; 120° , the ratio of moments between the outer and inner axle shafts changes from K_g up to $1/K_g$;
2. Variable moments provide a change in traction over a wide range;
3. The differential provides fast movement of the vehicle on a curvilinear section of the road as well as at turning;
4. The torques decreases so much that the wheels stop slipping and the differential blocks;
5. When most of the torque is transferred to the lagging wheel, the difference in angular velocities decreases. In this case, the angular velocity of the driving wheels is equalized, as a result the differential is locked [2]; In a pulsating differential (Fig. 2), is possible to apply round gears 1, 2, 3 with variable pitch (Fig. 3) [5].

Fig. 3. Pulsating differential with having variable pitch round bevel gears

The function of the variable gear ratio of the differential is determined by the relations:

$$(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = \left(\frac{P_t + \Delta P_t^1}{P_t - \Delta P_t} \right)^2; (u_{12}^7)_{\min} = \left(\frac{P_t - \Delta P_t^1}{P_t + \Delta P_t} \right)^2;$$

Let's accept as an example: $(P_t + \Delta P_t)_{\max} = 6$; $(P_t + \Delta P_t)_{\min} = 4$; $(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = 2,25$;
 $(u_{12}^7)_{\min} = 0,44$; $D = 5,11$. From the given example it is clear that the blocking coefficient for an asymmetric differential is $K_g = 2,25$.

In the pulsating differential (Fig. 2) it is possible to use round bevel eccentric gears (Fig. 4). The function of the gear ratio is determined by the dependencies:

$$(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = \left(\frac{a + e \cos \varphi_1}{a - e \cos \varphi_1} \right)^2; (u_{12}^7)_{\min} = \left(\frac{a - e \cos \varphi_1}{a + e \cos \varphi_1} \right)^2,$$

Let's assume as example: $a = 30$ mm; $e = 5$ mm. Then

$$(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = 2,96; (u_{12}^7)_{\min} = 0,5; D = 5,92.$$

In the pulsating differential (Fig. 2) it is possible to use spherical (Fig. 5) and ellipsoidal (Fig. 6) gears 1,2 that are rigidly attached.

Fig. 4. Pulsating differential with eccentric bevel

Fixed on axle shafts 3, 4 of wheels A and B wheels, full-length straight teeth 5 of gears 1, 2 are engaged with having incomplete length teeth 6 of toroidal satellite gear 7 that are located along spatial curves 8 of gears. Gear 7 rotates freely on axles 9 of differential housing 10.

Fig. 4. Pulsating differential with spherical with spherical gears

The gear ratio and adjustment range are determined by the following dependencies: for differential (Fig. 5)

$$(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = \left(\frac{r_{\max} \cos \varphi}{r_{\min}} \right)^2; (u_{12}^7)_{\min} = \left(\frac{r_{\min}}{r_{\max} \cos \varphi} \right)^2; D = \left(\frac{r_{\max} \cos \varphi}{r_{\min}} \right)^4 \quad (5)$$

for differential (Fig. 6)

$$(u_{12}^7)_{\max} = \left(\frac{r_{\max} R_1 \cos \varphi}{r_{\min} R} \right)^2; (u_{12}^7)_{\min} = \left(\frac{r_{\min} R}{r_{\max} R_1 \cos \varphi} \right)^2; D = \left(\frac{r_{\max} R_1 \cos \varphi}{r_{\min} R} \right)^4 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 5. Pulsating differential with ellipsoidal gears

where: r_{max}, r_{min} - are the maximum and minimum radii of satellite gear; R - are the radii of ellipsoid gear on sphere and major surface of torus; R_1 - are the radii of ellipsoid gear on sphere and major surface of torus; φ - is the variable angle between major surface of torus of gears 1, 2 and current radii R, R_1 .

As an example for differential (Fig.5) let's assume: $r_{max} = 22$ mm; $r_{min} = 7$ mm;

$$R = 20 \text{ mm}; \varphi_{max} = 55^\circ; \text{ then } (u_{12}^7)_{max} = 3,25; (u_{12}^7)_{min} = 0,31; D = 10,48.$$

For differential (Fig. 6) let's assume: $r_{max} = 27$ mm; $r_{min} = 7$ mm; $R = 20$ mm; $R_1 = 25$ mm; $\varphi_{min} = 65^\circ$; then $(u_{12}^7)_{max} = 4,15$; $(u_{12}^7)_{min} = 0,24$; $D = 17,29$; $D = 17,29$.

From the stated examples is clear that the blocking coefficient for asymmetric pulsating differentials is equal to: for the differential (Fig. 5) $K_g = -3,25$, for differential (Fig. 6) $K_g = -4,15$.

For this blocking coefficient the probability of full engagement of the drive wheels is: for the differential (Fig. 5) 76.2%, for differential (Fig. 6) 97.3%.

As an example, using the Willis formula, we will determine the maximum and minimum number of revolutions and torques of wheel B. To do this, we will use the dependencies:

$$(n_B)_{max} = \frac{(1 + U_{AB}^{max})n_6 - n_A}{(U_{AB})_{max}}; (n_B)_{min} = \frac{(1 + U_{AB}^{min})n_6 - n_A}{(U_{AB})_{min}} \tag{7}$$

$$(T_2)_{max} = (u_{12}^7)_{max} T_1; (T_2)_{min} = (u_{12}^7)_{min} T_1$$

Let's assume: $T_1 = 100$ Nm; $n_A = 10$ rpm; $n_6 = 10$ rpm.

The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Type of differential	$(n_B)_{max}$ rpm	$(n_B)_{min}$ rpm	$(T_2)_{max}$ Nm	$(T_2)_{min}$ Nm
1. With elliptical gears	59,37	22,5	394	25,4
2. With spherical gears	52	23	325	31
3. With eccentric gears	40	17,47	295	50
4. With elliptical gears	25,53	22,4	415	24
5. With round variable pitch gears	15,55	13,05	225	44

From analysis is clear that at vehicle turn and slide, the number of revolutions of the drive wheels and acting on them torques are changing over a wide range that contributes to the rapid movement of the vehicle.

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